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Parents as Social Context, Social Skills and Emotional Intelligence: A Path Model on Psychological Well-Being of Students

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the best-fit path model on the psychological well-being of students as estimated by parents as social context, social skills and emotional intelligence of senior high school students among public schools in Region XI. The study used descriptive correlational research using path analysis. The 400 students were determined using the stratified sampling procedure. Mean, Pearson r and path analysis were used as statistical tools. Results showed that the level of parents as social context, social skills and psychological well-being of students were high while emotional intelligence was very high. Findings indicated that parents as social context, social skills and emotional intelligence were significantly correlated with the psychological well-being of students. Model 3 came out as the best-fit path model that predicted the psychological well-being of students and it was significantly influenced by social skills of students, parents as social context and emotional intelligence. Social skills of students revealed a significant predictor of parents as social context while emotional intelligence showed a significant correlation with students' social skills. Hence, schools may consider enhancing the psychological well-being of students by developing their social skills and enhancing their emotional intelligence. Also, parents' engagement in school activities may be encouraged.

Keywords: *parents as social context, social skills, emotional intelligence, psychological well-being*

Introduction

Issues on the psychological well-being of students have been investigated by most researchers across countries. Most studies revealed that the psychological well-being of today's students is at risk. They have been identified as a vulnerable population, because at their age coincides with problem behaviors, and mental health problems such as depression and anxiety. These psychosocial problems of students have been progressively highlighted not for their increased incidence and severity, but also the close link to negative quality of life, such as poor academic performance, decreased life satisfaction, and even suicidal thoughts. In addition, students who have poor well-being in terms of physical and psychological can experience negative academic life (Eisenberg et al., 2009; Tobolowsky, 2018; Wynaden et al., 2013; Hadar et al., 2020).

Relative to this, students' psychological well-being is important for their overall learning. The well-being of students in terms of psychosocial and emotional, resilience, and moral well-being has been increasingly emphasized in recent years particularly for its relationship with student academic achievement. On a personal level, studies have shown that personal well-being such as interpersonal confidence, social and emotional skills, and self-esteem were associated with better adjustment and learning achievement. Hence, focusing on these attributes represents a promising approach to enhance students' learning gains (Eisenberg et al., 2009; Stamp et al., 2015; Roth & Brooks-Gunn, 2013; Yu et al., 2018; Sa et al., 2019).

In addition, studies have revealed the factors which influence the psychological well-being of students. In the study of Gupta and Mehtani (2015), it was explained that parents as social context of a child who practice particular child rearing patterns nurtures the child physically and contributes to overall psychological well-being. For instance, research findings indicated that an authoritative parenting style produced positive developmental outcomes, especially in the psychological and social positions in children. Similarly, Hasumi, Ahsan, Couper, Aguayo, and Jacobsen (2012), Papadakis, Zaranis, and Kalogiannakis (2019) conducted research on parental involvement and the mental well-being of Indian adolescents 13-14 years old. The study revealed that parental involvement decreased with increasing age, while poor mental health was significantly associated with a decreased likelihood of parental involvement (low levels of depression, loneliness, and anxiety). The study recommended health care professionals to encourage parents to be actively involved in adolescents' lives for development of psychological well-being). Moreover, it was also described in the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child that the state shall prioritize the well-being of the child and that the child should be free from any form of violence (Sichon, & Guhao Jr., 2020).

Furthermore, a study had indicated that social skills can predict psychological well-being. Well-being is a broad term capturing the importance of both psychological and physical exploration and health in one's life. Mental health and well-being require proper attention. Emotionally disturbed adolescents exhibit their impairment in a variety of ways such as failing academically, having poor self-images, having poor peer relationships and additionally, they may have little respect for the law of their society and adults. Academic failure and social rejection have a lasting consequence, as a failure to learn in school limits a person's chance to succeed in the future. Evidence suggests that social skills interventions can reduce many of these problems and can reduce the symptoms of depression and life-satisfaction. Social skills were also predicted to be associated with a reduction in the experience of stress and have a strong relationship with growth and development (Hendren et al., 2014; Nair et al., 2013; Guerra-Bustamante et al., 2019). Further, emotional intelligence has also gained attention as a focus of research and intervention for its promise as a set of skills that can be

taught to promote well-being (Schutte et al., 2007; Martins et al., 2010; Alvarez et al., 2015, 2016; Fernandez-Berrocal, 2016; Toscano-Hermoso et al., 2020).

In addition, various literature and related studies are herein presented that lead to the understanding of the variables under consideration i.e., parents as social context, social skills, emotional intelligence and psychological well-being.

For the variable Parents as Social Context., literature discusses that parenting or child rearing is the process of promoting and supporting the physical, emotional, social and intellectual development of a child from infancy to adulthood. Parenting refers to the intricacies of raising a child and not exclusively on the biological relationship. Parenting skills vary, and a parent with good parenting skills may be referred to as a good parent. Also, parenting styles vary by historical time period, race/ethnicity, social class, and other social features. Additionally, research has supported that parental history both in terms of attachments of varying quality as well as parental psychopathology, particularly in the wake of adverse experiences, can strongly influence parental sensitivity and child outcomes (Brooks, 2012; Bernstein, 2018; Grienberger, Kelly & Slade, 2015; Johri, 2014; Lieberman, Padron, Van Horn & Harris, 2015; Schechter & Willheim, 2009; Posey-Maddox & Haley-Lock, 2020).

Relatively, children's development of the cognitive and social skills needed for later success in school may be best supported by a parenting style known as responsive parenting. Responsiveness is an aspect of supportive parenting described across different theories and research frameworks (e.g. attachment, socio-cultural) as playing an important role in providing a strong foundation for children to develop optimally. Parenting that provides positive affection and high levels of warmth and is responsive in ways that are contingently linked to a young child's signals ("contingent responsiveness") are the affective-emotional aspects of a responsive style. These aspects, in combination with behaviors that are cognitively responsive to the child's needs, including the provision of rich verbal input and maintaining and expanding on the child's interests, provide the range of support necessary for multiple aspects of a child's learning (Landry, 2014; Garcia-Carrion et al., 2019).

The first domain of parents as social context is warmth. Warmth is the single most important and ubiquitous dimension of caregiving, prominent in almost all conceptualizations of parenting. Often labeled as acceptance, warmth refers to the expression of affection, love, appreciation, kindness, and regard; it includes emotional availability, support, and genuine caring. Expressions of warmth and involvement are especially salient when a child seeks comfort, but they can also be found in parent – child interactions focusing on teaching or discipline as well (Skinner, Johnson & Snyder, 2005; Gniewosz, Katstaller & Gniewosz, 2023).

The second domain is rejection. Parents are rejecting when they actively dislike their children. Expressions of rejection include aversion, hostility, harshness, over reactivity, irritability and explosiveness; they also include overt communication of negative feelings for the child, such as criticism, derision, and disapproval. Often referred to as hostility, parental rejection can be expressed in reaction to child bids for help and attention, or it can be initiated by the parent, independent of the child's behavior (Skinner et al., 2005; Mendoza-Lázaro, Santiago, Benito León-del-Barco, María-Isabel Polo-del-Río, Rocío Yuste-Tosina, & Víctor-María López-Ramos, 2019).

The third domain is structure. When it first appeared in the parenting literature in discussions of discipline and control, structure referred to the provision of clear expectations for mature behavior combined with consistent and appropriate limit setting. Also described as firm control, structure was a defining feature of parenting that was authoritative in discipline and communication (Baumrind, 2017).

The fourth domain is chaos. The construct of lax control can be broadened, so that the conceptual opposite of structure is chaos. Chaos goes beyond lack of structure to refer to parenting behaviors that are noncontingent, inconsistent, erratic, unpredictable, undependable, arbitrary, or, in general, interfere with or obscure the pathways from means to ends. In work on micro-environments, chaos is considered a kind of environmental confusion, which includes disorganization and hubbub (Matheny et al., 2015; Skinner & Wellborn, 2014; Marsh, Dobson, & Maddison, 2020).

The fifth indicator is autonomy support. Definitions of parental autonomy support, or autonomy granting, originally focused on the absence of psychological control or coercion. Support for autonomy extends beyond allowing children freedom of choice and expression to communicating genuine respect and deference and encouraging children to actively discover, explore, and articulate their own views, goals, and preferences. Autonomy support characterizes interactions in which children are expected to express their views and opinions and in which these are given weight in planning and problem solving (Barber, 2016; Skinner et al., 2005; Costa, Gugliandolo, Barberis, Cuzzocrea & Liga, 2019)

The last domain is coercion. Referred to as psychological control, coercive parenting describes a restrictive overcontrolling intrusive autocratic style in which strict obedience is demanded. It is a key feature of authoritarian parenting. Further, coercion has been linked to both internalizing and externalizing problems in adolescence (Barber, 2016; Baumrind, 2017; Meter D.J., Ehrenreich S.E. & Underwood M.K., 2019).

In terms of the variable Social Skills, literature discusses that social skills are considered one of the important factors in the success or failure of every individual in a society. In fact, well-informed teachers of young children recognize the importance of children's social development. The development of social skills lays a critical foundation for later academic achievement as well as work-related skills. Further, social skills are a collection of learned behaviors giving the individual the ability to have an influential relationship with others and to abstain from socially unreasonable reactions. Cooperation, collaborating with others, helping, initiating a relationship, requesting

help and praising and appreciating others are some examples of this type of behavior. Learning the above behaviors and creating influential relationships with others are most important in childhood. Unfortunately, some children do not learn these skills, which is why most of these children encounter negative reactions from adults and other children (Agran, Hughes, Thoma & Scott, 2016; Davies, Cooper, Kettler & Elliott, 2015; Gresham, 2016; Lynch & Simpson, 2010; Yoder, 2015; Panayiotou, Humphrey & Wigelsworth, 2019).

Further, social skills are behaviors enabling individuals to interact influentially and to abstain from undesirable responses. They represent the individuals' social and behavioral health success. These skills have their roots in cultural and social foundations and include behaviors such as pioneering in the establishment of new communications, requesting help, and making suggestions to help others. One of the most important educational aims of childhood is to develop social skills, and the level of children's and adults' enjoyment of these skills is influential in their personal and social health and their educational success (Morgan et al., 2015; Rawles, 2016; Klos et al., 2020).

The Social Skills scale is divided into seven subscales: communication, cooperation, assertion, responsibility, empathy, engagement, and self-control. First, the communication subscale includes behaviors such as making eye contact when talking and saying "please" and "thank you." Second, the cooperation subscale includes behaviors such as following rules and completing tasks without bothering others. Third, the assertion subscale includes behaviors such as asks for help when needed and says when there's a problem. Fourth, the responsibility subscale includes behaviors such as respecting the property of others and is well-behaved when unsupervised. Fifth, empathy subscale includes behaviors such as tries to comfort others and feels bad when others are sad. Sixth, the engagement subscale includes behaviors such as inviting others to join in activities, making friends easily, and introducing himself to others. Lastly, the self-control subscale includes behaviors such as stays calm when teased and uses appropriate behavior when upset (Gresham & Elliott, 2008; Duckworth et al., 2019).

As to Emotional Intelligence, it is stated that emotional Intelligence (EI) competencies have been shown to predict organizational effectiveness in many countries of the world. It is stated that emotional intelligence can be conceptualized relative to individuals' awareness of their own emotions and their ability to express those emotions, to individuals' perceptions of and awareness of emotions expressed by others (Austin, 2014; Boyatzis & Sala, 2014; Day & Carroll, 2014; Dulewicz & Higgs, 2013; Morand, 2011; Kanesan et al., 2019).

Further, it was suggested that emotional intelligence is a convenient phrase with which it is easier to focus attention on human talent. Even though it is a simple phrase, it incorporates the complexity of a person's capability. Based on extensive research Goleman has proposed five dimensions of emotional intelligence which are self-awareness, self-regulation, self-motivation, empathy (or social awareness) and social skills (Boyatzis et al., 2010; Singh, 2004; MacCann et al., 2020).

Self-awareness is the first component of emotional intelligence—which means having a deep understanding of one's emotions, strengths, weaknesses, needs, and drives (Escosora & Guhao 2023). People with strong self-awareness are neither overly critical nor unrealistically hopeful. Rather, they are honest—with themselves and with others (Goleman, 2014; Mahoney, Weissberg et al., 2021).

The second component is self-regulation, which is like an ongoing inner conversation and is the component of emotional intelligence that frees us from being prisoners of our feelings (Goleman, 2014).

The third component is motivation. If there is one trait that virtually all effective individuals have, it is motivation. They are driven to achieve beyond expectations—their own and everyone else's. The key word here is achieved. Plenty of people are motivated by external factors, such as a big salary or the status that comes from having an impressive title or being part of a prestigious company. By contrast, those with leadership potential are motivated by a deeply embedded desire to achieve for the sake of achievement (Goleman, 2014; Trigueros et al., 2019),

The fourth component is empathy or social awareness. Of all the dimensions of emotional intelligence, empathy is the most easily recognized. We have all felt the empathy of a sensitive teacher or friend; we have all been struck by its absence in an unfeeling coach or boss. But when it comes to business, we rarely hear people praised, let alone rewarded, for their empathy (Goleman, 2014; Moudatsou et al., 2020).

Lastly, social skill refers to friendliness with a purpose: moving people in the direction you desire, whether that's agreement on a new marketing strategy or enthusiasm about a new product (Goleman, 2014; Perez, Geronimo & Castilla, 2019).

As to Psychological Well-Being, it is explained that students' well-being is important for their overall learning. The well-being of students in terms of psychosocial, emotional, resilience and moral well-being has been increasingly emphasized in recent years particularly for its relationship with student academic achievement. In a personal level, studies have shown that personal well-being such as interpersonal confidence, social and emotional skills, and self-esteem were associated with better adjustment and learning achievement. Hence, focusing on these attributes represents a promising approach to enhance students' learning gains (Eisenberg et al., 2009; Stamp et al., 2015; Roth & Brooks-Gunn, 2013; Yu et al., 2018; Rehman et al., 2020).

The first indicator of student well-being is autonomy. Autonomy is defined as a sense of self-determination and being able to resist social pressure to think and behave in certain ways. The second indicator is environmental mastery. Environmental Mastery involves a sense of mastery and competence in managing the environment to meet personal needs, desires, and values. The third indicator is

personal growth. Personal Growth centers on a sense of improvement and development in self over time and making the most of one's talent and capacities. The fourth indicator is positive relations. Positive Relations with Others centers on developing and maintaining warm, satisfying and trusting interpersonal relationships. The fifth indicator is purpose in life. Purpose in Life refers to a sense of meaning of life and directedness. Lastly, self-acceptance as the last indicator refers to feeling positive about oneself and the past, even when one is aware of his or her own shortcomings (Lee & Taniguchi, 2017; De-Juanas et al., 2020).

Further, the researcher explored related studies which revealed the relationship of the variables such as the parents as social context, social skills and emotional intelligence of students with psychological well-being. In the study of Gupta and Mehtani (2015), it was explained that parents as social context of a child who practice particular child rearing patterns nurtures the child physically and contributes to overall psychological well-being. For instance, research findings indicated that an authoritative parenting style produced positive developmental outcomes, especially in the psychological and social positions in them. Similarly, Hasumi, Ahsan, Couper, Aguayo and Jacobsen (2012) investigated parental involvement and mental well-being of Indian adolescents (13-14 years). The study revealed that parental involvement decreased with increasing age, while poor mental health was significantly associated with a decreased likelihood of parental involvement (low levels of depression, loneliness, and anxiety). The study recommended health care professionals to encourage parents to be actively involved in adolescents lives for development of psychological well-being.

Moreover, a study has indicated that social skills can predict psychological wellbeing. Well-being is a broad term capturing the importance of both psychological and physical exploration and health in one's life. Mental health and well-being require proper attention. Emotionally disturbed adolescents exhibit their impairment in a variety of ways such as failing academically, having poor self-images, having poor peer relationships and additionally, they may have little respect for the law of their society and adults. Academic failure and social rejection have a lasting consequence, as a failure to learn in school limits a person's chance to succeed in the future. Evidence suggests that social skills interventions can reduce many of these problems and can reduce the symptoms of depression and life-satisfaction. Social skills were also predicted to be associated with a reduction in the experience of stress and with a strong relationship with growth and development (Hendren et al., 2014; Nair et al., 2013). Further, emotional intelligence also has gained attention as a focus of research and intervention for its promise as a set of skills that can be taught to promote well-being (Schutte et al., 2007; Martins, Ramalho & Morin, 2010; Alvarez, Extremera & Fernandez-Berrocal, 2015, 2016; Fernandez-Berrocal, 2016; Collie, 2022).

Furthermore, the foregoing presentation and discussion of various literatures have helped in bringing into focus the important variables of the study, ie., parents as social context, social skills, emotional intelligence, and psychological well-being. These served as support to the results and findings of the study.

Consequently, the main thrust of this study was to determine the best-fit path model of psychological well-being of students as estimated by parents as social context, social skills, and emotional intelligence of students among public schools in Region XI. Specifically, this study aimed to describe parents' level as social context in terms of warmth, rejection, structure, chaos, autonomy support, and coercion. It also aimed to ascertain the level of social skills of students in terms of communication, cooperation, assertion, responsibility, empathy, engagement, and self-control. Further, it ascertained the level of emotional intelligence of students in terms of self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, social awareness/empathy, and social skills. Also, it determined the level of psychological well-being of students in terms of autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations, purpose in life, and self-acceptance. Additionally, it determined the significance of the relationship between the following parents as social context and psychological well-being of students, between social skills and psychological well-being of students, and between emotional intelligence and psychological well-being of students. Lastly, it determined the best-fit path model of the psychological well-being of students among public elementary schools.

The study was anchored on the Self-Determination Theory of Ryan and Deci (2007). This theory explains the concept of wellbeing that is characteristic of the eudemonic approaches of well-being focusing on the fact that full functionality is related to vitality, self-awareness, and self-regulated behavior. The main focus of this approach is on a healthy functioning self, involving the integrated structures, processes as fundamentals of autonomous functioning, rather than those attainment of rewards, status, and esteem. Being fully functioning is determined by various factors such as developmental (emotional intelligence), and social (parents). Hence, this theory can explain that psychological well-being is affected by parents as social context, social skills, and emotional intelligence.

In consonance with the above objectives, the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance stating that there is no significant relationship between the following parents as social context and psychological well-being of students, between social skills and psychological well-being of students, and between emotional intelligence and psychological well-being of students. It was also hypothesized that there is no best-fit path model of the psychological well-being of students among public elementary schools.

Significantly, in the context of learning, assessing students' psychological well-being has been an important concern being explored by most researchers across the globe. The well-being of students in terms of psychosocial, emotional, resilience, and moral well-being has been increasingly emphasized in recent years particularly for its relationship with student academic achievement. In a personal level, studies have shown that personal well-being such as interpersonal confidence, social and emotional skills, and self-esteem were associated with better adjustment and learning achievement. Hence, focusing on these attributes represents a promising approach to enhance students' learning gains (Eisenberg et al., 2009; Stamp et al., 2015; Roth & Brooks-Gunn, 2013; Yu et al., 2018, Morales-

Rodriguez, Espigares-Lopez, & Perez-Marmol, 2020). This study aimed to explore the relationship between parents as social context, social skills, emotional intelligence, and psychological well-being among students in public schools in Region XI. Anchored on the Self-Determination Theory, the research delved into the significance of these factors in shaping students' overall well-being. Null hypotheses were tested to determine the absence of significant relationships and to ascertain the best-fit path model for psychological well-being. The study holds relevance in the educational landscape, emphasizing the importance of assessing students' well-being for their academic achievement and personal development, echoing findings from previous research.

The implications of this study extend to various stakeholders in education. For the Department of Education, school heads, teachers, and pupils, the findings offer insights into fostering a conducive learning environment that promotes parental involvement, social-emotional skills, and psychological well-being. Recommendations derived from the research may inform policy formulation, curriculum development, and teacher training programs aimed at enhancing students' holistic development. Additionally, the study provides parents with valuable guidance on nurturing their children's social skills, emotional intelligence, and overall well-being, thereby contributing to their success in the 21st-century learning context. Moreover, the research serves as a foundation for future studies, inviting further exploration into related variables and educational interventions.

The findings of this study may be beneficial to the Department of Education, school heads, teachers, pupils and even the future researchers. The result of the study may give information to the Department of Education officials regarding the parents as social context of students, social skills and emotional intelligence of students and their psychological well-being which may serve as the basis for the formulation of plans and programs that may augment these factors which are important for student learning, academic success, and life-long learning skills. Also, they may provide more in-service trainings and seminars that may help enhance the capability of teachers to establish school learning environment which help promote strong parental involvement, social and emotional skills of students which consequently augment their psychological well-being.

Moreover, the result of the study may be beneficial to the school heads since they may acquire ample knowledge and information about how to implement programs which will assist the development of these factors of students' learning. Specifically, the school heads may strengthen school-parent linkage and partnership especially in planning and in conducting intervention programs that address students' social emotional and psychological problems inside and outside the school.

Consequently, findings of this study may also help the parents understand their role in developing the social skills, emotional intelligence, and psychological well-being of their children. Parents may be able to adapt helpful parenting styles especially when dealing with students' behaviors and learning styles in the 21st century context. In addition, the findings of this study may benefit the pupils in such a way that they develop their social skills, emotional intelligence, and psychological well-being. Likewise, this study would serve as springboard of future researchers for further studies about the related variables and related studies.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative, non-experimental research design utilizing the correlational technique. The correlational technique is a non-experimental approach in which researchers investigate the relationships between variables in a natural setting without manipulation or control. In correlational studies, researchers assess the strength of connections between variables by examining how changes in one variable are associated with changes in another variable. Typically, the correlational method involves independent and dependent variables, but the impact of the independent variable is observed on the dependent variable without actively manipulating the independent variable (Creswell, 2002).

This research also utilized Path Modeling. Path analysis, developed by Wright in 1921, serves to quantify the connections between numerous variables. It elucidates causal relationships among variables, with a typical application being mediation. In mediation, it is assumed that a variable can impact an outcome both directly and indirectly through the influence of another variable (Fan et al., 2016).

Furthermore, path analysis offers a valuable structure for defining and evaluating presumed causal connections among sets of measured variables (Hancock & Schoonen, 2015). In the realm of educational research, Stage et al. (2004) assessed the application of path analyses, highlighting its purpose in providing estimates for the extent and significance of hypothesized causal relationships among sets of variables, illustrated through the utilization of path diagrams. In the context of this study, path analysis was employed to examine the relationships among parents as social context, social skills, emotional intelligence, and psychological well-being of students in public schools in Region XI, Philippines.

Respondents

The study was conducted among public secondary schools in Region XI, Philippines, and the location of each province or division. Davao Region, designated as Region XI, is located in the southeastern portion of the island of Mindanao. It is bounded on the north by the provinces of Surigao del Sur, Agusan del Sur, and Bukidnon, on the east by the Philippine Sea, and on the west by the Central Mindanao provinces. It is composed of five provinces – Davao del Sur, Davao del Norte, Davao Oriental, Davao Occidental and Davao de Oro. It also boasts of six cities – Davao, Tagum, Island Garden City of Samal, Panabo, Mati and Digos – that continue to showcase

a vibrant investment climate because of its global competitiveness. In the areas mentioned above, survey questionnaires were distributed.

The respondents of the study were the 400 senior high school students among public schools who represented 74,214 senior high school students in Region XI for the school year 2022-2023. The reason the researcher picked senior high school students for this study is because they are at an important age. In high school, teens are going through big changes in how they think, feel, and interact with others. Studying this age group helps us understand how parents still influence them, especially as they deal with high school challenges and make choices about their future. We want to see how family, social skills, and emotional smarts play a role in their well-being during this crucial time. Looking at senior high school students gives us practical ideas on how to support them and improve their overall happiness during this important phase of growing up.

The study employed the Stratified Random Method to select participants. This sampling technique involves dividing the overall population into smaller subgroups, known as strata. In stratified random sampling, these strata are created based on shared characteristics among members, such as income or educational attainment. This method is also referred to as Proportional Random Sampling or Quota Random Sampling (Hayes, 2020).

Instruments

The modified survey questionnaire used in this study was made up of four parts which are anchored on an adapted questionnaire, i.e., parents as social context, social skills, emotional intelligence, and psychological well-being. The questionnaires underwent modification and validation by experts. The initial version of the research instrument was presented to the research adviser for feedback, suggestions, and recommendations to enhance its clarity, with the proposed corrections incorporated. The refined versions were then submitted to a panel of experts for further improvement. The final revision was carried out by integrating corrections, comments, and suggestions provided by the expert validators prior to the data collection phase. The consolidated evaluation from the experts yielded an average weighted mean of 4.50, corresponding to an excellent verbal description. Additionally, prior to administering the research instrument, a pilot test was conducted with a group of students who were not part of the main study's respondents. The survey questionnaire used in the pilot test underwent reliability testing through the Internal Consistency Method. This method was deemed most suitable as the test consisted of dichotomously scored items, where examinees either passed or failed each item. The calculated reliability of the instrument was 0.734 for the parents as social context questionnaire, 0.844 social skills of student's questionnaire, 0.890 emotional intelligence questionnaire and 0.865 psychological well-being questionnaire, all assessed using Cronbach Alpha.

The questionnaire for parents as social context was adapted from Skinner, Johnson, and Snyder (2005) and was modified to fit the study and subjected to the validation of the experts. The parents as social context scale have the following indicators: warmth, rejection, structure, chaos, autonomy support and coercion. The level of parents as social context obtained an overall mean of 3.63 or higher, with a standard deviation of 0.393 this means that the parents as social context of senior high school students among public schools was oftentimes manifested. Further, the questionnaire for social skills was adapted from Gresham & Elliott (2008). It was modified to fit to the study and was subjected to the validation of the experts. The questionnaire for social skills has the following indicators: communication, cooperation, assertion, responsibility, empathy, engagement and self-control.

On the other hand, for the level of social skills of students, computations yielded a grand mean of 3.88 or high, with a standard deviation of 0.419, and this indicates that the social skills of students are oftentimes manifested.

Also, the questionnaire for emotional intelligence was adapted from Singh (2004). It was modified to fit to the study and was subjected to the validation of the experts. The questionnaire for the emotional intelligence of students has the following indicators: self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, social awareness/empathy, and social skills.

For the level of emotional intelligence of students, computations yielded a grand mean of 3.79 or high, with a standard deviation of 0.455; this indicates that the emotional intelligence of students is oftentimes manifested.

Moreover, the questionnaire for psychological well-being was adapted from Lee and Taniguchi (2013). It was modified to fit in to the study and will be subjected to the validation of the experts. The questionnaire for the psychological well-being of students has the following indicators: autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations, purpose in life, and self-acceptance. Consequently, on the level of psychological well-being of students, computations yielded a grand mean of 3.88 or high, with a standard deviation of 0.496; this indicates that the psychological well-being of students among public schools is oftentimes manifested.

Procedure

During the data collection process, the researcher sought approval from the Regional Director of DepEd-Region XI, followed by requests to various Schools Division Superintendents. After obtaining their consent, the researcher then sought permission from District Supervisors in each selected district and the respective School Heads. This was done to secure approval for conducting the study involving 400 senior high school students. Once approval was granted, the researcher personally distributed and administered the research instruments.

The Path – Goal Theory of Leadership of House & Mitchell (1974) was used to test the hypothesized models and determine the best

fit model for the school effectiveness among public schools. In evaluating the goodness of fit of the models, the following indices were computed as follows:

<i>INDEX</i>	<i>CRITERION</i>
P-close	> 0.05
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2
P-value	> 0.05
GFI	> 0.95
CFI	> 0.95
NFI	> 0.95
TLI	> 0.95
RMSEA	< 0.05

Legend: CMIN/DF, Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom; NFI, Normed Fit Index; TLI, Tucker-Lewis Index; CFI, Comparative Fit Index; GFI, Goodness of Fit Index; RMSEA, Root Means Square of Error Approximation; P-close, P of Close Fit; P-value, Probability Level

While conducting the survey questionnaire, the researcher ensured minimal disruption to the ongoing classes. Throughout the questionnaire administration, the researcher personally attended to any queries or requests for clarification from the respondents. Once the respondents had completed the questionnaire, the researcher collected all the administered questionnaires. After successfully retrieving the questionnaires, the collected data were organized and tabulated. To derive the required information for interpretation and further analysis, appropriate statistical tools were employed.

Mean was used to describe the level of parents as social context, social skills, emotional intelligence, and psychological well-being of students in answer to sub-problems 1 to 4. Pearson r was used to determine the significance of the relationship between the psychological well-being of students and the independent variables (parents as social context, social skills, and emotional intelligence) in answer to sub-problem 5. The path model was used to determine the best-fit path model of the psychological well-being of students among public schools.

In the conduct of this study, ethical issues and considerations were dealt with. The researcher had undergone evaluation conducted by the members of ethics review committee. After several review processes, this study was marked as passed and approved by the UM Ethics Review Committee (UMERC). In terms of voluntary participations, the researcher ensured that the participation of the respondents was completely voluntary and anonymous to protect their privacy and information was given whenever the respondents will not understand, before deciding whether to participate or not in the study. The researcher was granted a certificate of approval with a UMERC Protocol Number 2022-157.

To ensure privacy and confidentiality, the records of this study were confidential as far as permitted by law. Any identifiable information which was obtained in connection with this study remained confidential, except if necessary to protect the respondents' rights or welfare. The researcher resisted the release of information about their participation to people who were not connected with the study. When the results of the study were published or discussed in conference, no identifiable information would be used. Thus, this research adhered to the Data Privacy Act of 2012 which protected the students from unauthorized processing of their private or identifiable information or guarantee them that their response cannot be traced back to its real sources to protect their identity.

Further, the respondents' name did not appear anywhere and no one except the researcher knew about respondents' specific answers. In line with the purpose of protecting the rights of the respondents, all the information gathered from this study were kept private and confidential.

Informed consent was also secured from all respondents involved in the study. The researcher conducted a detailed and comprehensive explanation regarding the purpose of the study to the respondents. The researcher ensured that the condition of the consent was a voluntary choice. The respondents had the sufficient information and adequate understanding of both the proposed research and the implications of their participation in the study so that the results will be utilized by the administrators for whatever purpose this may serve them best. The most important thing was that the form must bear the signature of the respondent which implies that he/she participated in the study voluntarily. Moreover, the respondents' personal and private information that were required in the study were treated with utmost care and were kept strictly confidential in accordance with the RA 10173 or Data Privacy Act of 2012 which ensured that all personal data shared were safeguarded and protected.

In terms of recruitment, the researcher ensured the appropriateness of identified recruiting parties and conducted a review of level of risks and measures to mitigate these risks (including physical, psychological, and social economic. The possible discomforts that were encountered by the respondents during the survey were managed by the recruiting parties, especially the researcher who was assisted by the school heads and teachers in meeting the number of respondents in the study.

As to risks, benefit and safety, this research did not involve high risk situations that the population may experience in physical, psychological, or socioeconomic concerns. It protected and secured the rights of the individuals in the study. Likewise, with the result of this study, the researcher yielded a generalizable knowledge about the condition of students. The results of this study can help the school heads and teachers since the findings of this study will give them new information about students' condition. The student respondents received tangible benefits such as a simple token from the researcher.

Moreover, the safety of the respondents was ensured using pseudonyms throughout the conduct of the research to protect their identities. Also, the data which were gathered from the survey were kept confidential and were utilized to verify the findings of the study. Further, the researcher ensured health protocols amid COVID-19 pandemic during the seeking of organization's permission and approval as well as during the administration of survey questionnaires. To ensure health and safety of everyone involved in the study, the researcher explicitly declared adherence to the COVID-19 protocol from the IATF and local ordinances.

In terms of the avoidance of plagiarism, the researcher had undergone the turn-it-in software to ensure that no trace/evidence of misrepresentation of someone else's work as his own. The researcher made sure that the correct and accurate way of citing ideas from other writers and scholars was fully observed. To be able to do this, this paper had undergone grammar checking via Grammarly software. As this study was based on several existing studies, the researcher made sure that he did not make any tale from his literature. Thus, all the information presented was carefully written and cited. All sources used in this study came from reliable journals and other scholarly works. This research complied with the citation rules set forth of APA 7th edition citation format hence there was no misrepresentation of work or alterations of any data gathered in the study. There was no making up of data and/or results, or purposefully putting forward conclusions that were not accurate. No inconsistency with the existing literature among the information was included in manuscript. In the same manner, falsification was also taken into consideration in which no trace of purposefully misrepresenting the work to fit a model or theoretical expectation. No evidence of overclaim or exaggerations.

Additionally, since the researcher is a public-school teacher from the intended research locale there is a conflict of interest (COI). Thus, the researcher ensured to clearly eliminate the COI. There was no set of conditions in which a professional judgment concerning primary interest such as the respondents' welfare or the validity of the research tends to be influenced by a secondary interest such as financial or academic gains or recognitions. The writings in this paper did not utilize any form of untruthfulness to harm the welfare of the respondents. All the information written was checked and validated by the panel of experts. Moreover, deceit was also avoided in which evidence that the benefit of misleading the respondents outweighs any potential harm to them.

In addition, the permission from the schools was ensured by the researcher. The researcher expressed getting a written permission from the organization in which the research had undertaken or the location in which the data was collected. When getting written permission, the researcher talked to the School Division Superintendent and concerned School Heads to give the permission sought and assured them that the activities were organized well in advance. Also, the survey questionnaires utilized in this study were clear and comprehensible; the researcher made sure that the respondents were fully aware of the benefits the school may get from the study though an informed consent. Thus, the survey was conducted with the approval of the concerned school authorities, as well as the permission of the respondents themselves.

Lastly, this study considered authorship qualifications in conduct of the study. The researcher together with the help and guidance of the research adviser substantially contributed to the conception and design, or acquisition of data, and its analysis and interpretation. The researcher and adviser collaboratively drafted the article and revised it critically for important intellectual content. Both contributed to the study leading to the publication of the research.

Results and Discussion

This section outlines data and findings from research instruments aimed at identifying the optimal path model for students' psychological well-being in public schools across Region XI, Philippines. It encompasses aspects such as parents' social context, students' social skills and emotional intelligence, and their overall psychological well-being. Subsequent subheadings explore the significance of relationships between these factors, concluding with an examination of the goodness of fit measures for three path analysis models.

Level of Parents as Social Context

The first objective of this study was to determine the level of parents as social context of students. The level of parents as social context among public schools is in terms of warmth, rejection, structure, chaos, autonomy support, and coercion. The data on the parents as social context in public schools is shown in Table 1. With a standard deviation of 0.393, the overall mean for the parents as social context was 3.63, which is high. This high level of parents as social context is due to the moderate to very high ratings of students on the domain warmth, rejection, structure, chaos, autonomy support, and coercion. This indicates that parents as social context of students was oftentimes manifested. The data further implies that those parents play a significant and influential role in the overall social environment of students within these educational institutions. This could be attributed to active parental involvement, positive interactions, and strong support networks, all of which contribute to a nurturing and conducive social context for students.

This aligns with the findings of several studies such as Vale and Maciel (2019) which found that parents' social representations of teachers can influence their students' perceptions of education. Similarly, it affirms the idea of García-Zambrano et al. (2022) highlighting the impact of the family context on students' learning, emphasizing the need for strategic activities to engage parents in their children's education. Likewise, it confirms the statement of Zborovsky and Shabrova (2021) discussing the potential for parents to become active participants in their children's education. Also, this is in line with study of Caridade et al. (2020) which underscored the importance of parental involvement in school activities involving students.

Table 1. *Level of Parents as Social Context*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Warmth	0.755	4.26	Very high
Rejection	0.866	3.10	Moderate
Structure	0.790	3.92	High
Chaos	0.817	2.99	Moderate
Autonomy support	0.837	4.06	High
Coercion	0.722	3.44	High
Overall	0.393	3.63	High

From this result, among the six indicators of parents as social context, warmth attained the highest mean score of 4.26 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.755 while chaos, the lowest, gained a mean score of 2.99 or moderate with a standard deviation of 0.817 which implies varied responses. This suggests that students perceive a strong and affirming emotional connection with their parents. This reflects a positive parental influence, fostering a supportive and affectionate social context. This aligns with the ideas of Parmar and Nathans (2022) stating that parental warmth is demonstrated through accepting, caring, and supportive parenting. Parental warmth is what students need as they are engaged academically.

The moderate level of chaos as domain of parents as social context suggests that parents sometimes create an environment characterized by inconsistent parental behavior, unfulfilled promises, unpredictability in expressions of anger and perceived arbitrary punishments. This further expands the statement of some authors such as Marsh et al. (2020) indicating that chaos in the family, characterized by disorganization and environmental confusion, is associated with a range of adverse outcomes for children. As stated by several authors (Coe et al., 2019; Marsh et al., 2020; Zvara et al., 2020), this includes lower quality parenting behaviors. Parents tend to be less sensitive and have more intrusive parenting behavior. These parents have dismissive attachment styles and disorganization which appeared to exacerbate parenting difficulties. This would result in an increased risk of behavior problems in students.

Level of Social Skills of Students

The second objective was to determine the level of social skills of students, which was measured through a survey questionnaire with the following indicators: communication, cooperation, assertion, responsibility, empathy, engagement, and self-control. Table 2 shows the data on the level of social skills of students.

Table 2. *Level of Social Skills of Students*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Communication	0.522	4.00	High
Cooperation	0.571	4.04	High
Assertion	0.654	3.72	High
Responsibility	0.613	4.18	High
Empathy	0.687	3.89	High
Engagement	0.664	3.73	High
Self-Control	0.636	3.58	High
Overall	0.419	3.88	High

Computations yielded a grand mean of 3.88 or high with a standard deviation of 0.419, and this indicates that the level of social skills of students is always manifested. This implies that the students consistently demonstrate strong interpersonal abilities, reflecting a strong and proficient aptitude in social interactions. This affirms the study of Wiguna et al. (2020) which found that high school students possess social skills that are crucial for their future success in the workplace and society. Similarly, it aligns with the ideas of Ninčević and Vukelić (2023) emphasizing the importance of social skills of students in bringing about effective social and communication competences and supportive teacher-student relationships.

Data reveals that the domain of social skills of students that yielded the highest mean score was the responsibility domain with a mean rating of 4.18 or high with a standard deviation of 0.613. On the other hand, the lowest indicator, albeit high, is self-control which got a mean score of 3.58 with standard deviation of 0.636. The high level of social skills of students in terms of responsibility indicates that students demonstrate considerate actions like respecting others' belongings, being well-behaved without supervision, and actively taking responsibility within both individual and group contexts. This is in line with the study of various authors (Abdulsamad & Majeed, 2020; Fonseca et al., 2019) indicating that students demonstrate a high level of social skills in terms of performing responsibility, particularly in terms of personal values and social commitment. This further supports the statement of Barkunova et al. (2021) that students with high level of responsibility in the social setting tend to demonstrate collectivist orientation, a preference for communication, and situational responsibility.

On the other hand, the high level of self-control of students indicates that the students' high self-control is demonstrated through their ability to make compromises, stay calm during conflicts or teasing, handle criticism without upset, use appropriate language when upset, and respond calmly to disagreements or physical provocation. This is parallel with the study of some authors (Agung et al., 2020; Maisepian et al., 2021) which reported high levels of self-control among high school students. Also, it aligns with the findings of the

study of Borzova and Plotnikova (2021) which identified above-average or high self-control as most favorable for self-realization in students. Further, it also supports the study of Nwagu et al. (2018) which found that students, particularly males, were exhibiting higher levels of self-control.

Level of Emotional Intelligence of Students

The third objective was to determine the level of emotional intelligence of students which was measured through a survey questionnaire with the following indicators: self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, social awareness/empathy, and social skills. Shown in Table 3 are the data on the level of emotional intelligence of students.

Table 3. Level of Emotional Intelligence of Students

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Self-Awareness	0.512	3.95	High
Self-Regulation	0.527	3.81	High
Motivation	0.554	3.98	High
Social	0.580	3.65	High
Awareness/Empathy			
Social Skills	0.580	3.56	High
Overall	0.455	3.79	High

Computations yielded a grand mean of 3.79 or high with a standard deviation of 0.455, and this indicates that the level of emotional intelligence of students is oftentimes manifested. This students' high level of emotional intelligence is evident in their adeptness at understanding and managing their own emotions, as well as their capacity to navigate interpersonal relationships with empathy and awareness in various emotional situations. This is similar to the findings of some authors (Kant, 2019; Kumar & Randhawa, 2022) which both found that secondary students exhibited high levels of emotional intelligence. It also affirms the statement of Ali (2020) which reported high emotional intelligence levels among students.

Data reveals that the domain of emotional intelligence of students that yielded the highest mean score is motivation with a mean rating of 3.98 or high with a standard deviation of 0.554. On the other hand, the lowest indicator, albeit high, is the social skills which got a mean score of 3.56 with standard deviation of 0.580. The high level of students' motivation is reflected in their continuous efforts to enhance performance, set challenging goals, and strive for achievement. Their proactive approach, belief in the correlation between willpower and success, and confidence under pressure collectively showcase a strong motivation characterized by determination, initiative, and a focus on long-term rewards. This confirms Pongračić et al. (2021) that students can exhibit high levels of motivation, particularly when they are interested and enthusiastic about their studies. Also, this aligns with the statement of some authors (Biktina, 2021; Edu et al., 2021) indicating that students with motivation show drive for achievement and readiness to overcome pressures. Students with high motivation tend to have personal characteristics such as spontaneity or focus.

Moreover, the high level of social skills of students is evident in their individual capacity to convincingly influence and impress others through effective communication, updated knowledge, and the ability to create an enthusiastic, collaborative atmosphere. This aligns with various studies (Morales et al., 2018; Wiguna et al., 2020) emphasizing the importance of social skills of students. Also, it affirms the ideas of some studies (Alonso-Aldana et al., 2022; Ninčević & Vukelić, 2023) which revealed that social skills are most likely used by students demonstrating communication and social competence.

Level of Psychological Well-being of Students

The fourth objective was to determine level of psychological well-being of students with the following indicators: autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations, purpose in life, and self-acceptance. Shown in Table 4 are the data on the level of psychological well-being of students. Computations yielded a grand mean of 3.88 or high with a standard deviation of 0.496, indicating that the psychological well-being of students is oftentimes manifested. This suggests a positive mental state of students. These students can navigate challenges, maintain positive relationships, and engage effectively in academic and personal pursuits. This is in parallel with the study of Morales-Rodríguez et al. (2020) which underscores the role of self-acceptance, positive relationships, autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth and purpose in life in shaping psychological well-being of students. It is stated that psychological well-being is viewed as the result of a life well-lived and is an important factor in students' lives. Students must adjust to a learning context. Moreover, it confirms the study of Walker (2009) which revealed that the psychological well-being of students steadily improved.

From this result, the indicator of psychological well-being of students that yielded the highest mean is purpose in life with a mean score of 4.06 or high, while the lowest indicator, albeit high is self-acceptance which gained a mean score of 3.76. The high level of students' purpose in life is evident in their forward-looking orientation, emphasizing future goals and accomplishments rather than present challenges. Their proactive approach to setting and valuing goals reflects a sense of direction, purpose, and a belief that there are meaningful tasks to be accomplished in life. This expands the findings of the study of Sharma and De Alba (2018) which revealed the sense of purpose among students considering their diverse backgrounds. Also, it aligns with the statement of Heng and Pereira (2020) stipulating students' purpose in high-performance schooling, revealing a prevalence of self-oriented academic achievement goals and

a proportion with beyond-the-self life goals.

Table 4. Level of Psychological Well-being of Students

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Autonomy	0.653	3.80	High
Environmental Mastery	0.669	3.82	High
Personal Growth	0.671	3.95	High
Positive Relations	0.707	3.89	High
Purpose in Life	0.654	4.06	High
Self-Acceptance	0.702	3.76	High
Overall	0.496	3.88	High

Moreover, the high level of self-acceptance of students is evident in their confident and positive feelings about themselves, along with a satisfying acknowledgment of academic achievements. This is similar to the finding of the study of Ballane (2019) which revealed a high level of self-acceptance among students. This also aligns with the study of Farhan (2020) which found that students with good self-acceptance demonstrate confidence, self-awareness and the ability to accept both strengths and weaknesses. Also, it confirms the idea of Verschueren et al. (2019) emphasizing the importance of how students perceive themselves as more accepted.

Significance on the Relationship between Parents as Social Context and Psychological Well-Being of Students

Table 5.1. Significance on the Relationship between Parents as Social Context and Psychological Well-Being of Students

Parents as Social Context	Psychological Well-Being of Students						Overall
	Autonomy	environmental mastery	personal growth	positive relations	purpose in life	self-acceptance	
Warmth	.236* (0.000)	.187* (0.000)	.204* (0.000)	.223* (0.000)	.136* (0.011)	.162* (0.002)	.261* (0.000)
Rejection	-.028 (0.604)	.016 (0.766)	-.039 (0.470)	.066 (0.221)	.016 (0.767)	.052 (0.336)	.020 (0.705)
structure	.146* (0.006)	.193* (0.000)	.184* (0.001)	.226* (0.000)	.160* (0.000)	.282* (0.000)	.272* (0.000)
Chaos	.048 (0.371)	.034 (0.526)	.052 (0.334)	.002 (0.965)	-.002 (0.976)	.038 (0.476)	.040 (0.461)
autonomy support	.193 (0.000)	.138* (0.000)	.193* (0.000)	.209* (0.000)	.262* (0.000)	.223* (0.000)	.277* (0.000)
Coercion	.159* (0.000)	.132* (0.013)	.192* (0.000)	.221* (0.000)	.156* (0.003)	.134* (0.012)	.227* (0.000)
Overall	.248* (0.000)	.232* (0.000)	.258* (0.000)	.315* (0.000)	.243* (0.000)	.299* (0.000)	.364* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level

One important purpose of this study was to determine whether parents as social context has a significant relationship with the psychological well-being of students. The results of the computations are shown in Table 5.1. As shown in the table, the overall r-value on the correlation between the level of parents as social context and the level of psychological well-being of students is 0.364 with $p < 0.05$, which means that parents as social context is significantly associated with students' psychological well-being. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Further, when the domains of parents such as warmth, rejection, structure, chaos, autonomy support and coercion, were correlated to the overall psychological well-being of students, results of the computation yielded the r-values of 0.261, 0.020, 0.272, 0.040, 0.277, and 0.0227 with the p-values of less than 0.05, respectively, which can be all interpreted as significant. These factors are significantly related to the domains of psychological well-being of students, such as autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations, purpose in life, and learning, and self-acceptance.

The result indicates that parents characterized by characteristics such as warmth, rejection, structure, chaos, autonomy support and coercion are directly associated to an overall psychological well-being of students. This connection implies that the nature of parental interaction, support, and overall environment plays a significant role in shaping the mental and emotional health of students. Recognizing and understanding parental influence can be crucial in addressing and promoting positive psychological well-being among students. This confirms the proposition of Gupta and Mehtani (2015) stating that parents as social context of a child contributes to overall psychological well-being. Similarly, it affirms the contention of Hasumi et al. (2012) and Mosley-Johnson, Garacci, Wagner, et al (2019) emphasizing the role of parents in improving child's development of psychological well-being.

Significance on the Relationship between Social Skills and Psychological Well-Being of Students

Another purpose of this study was to determine whether the variable social skills of students have a significant relationship with their psychological well-being. The results of the computations are shown in Table 5.2. As shown in the table, the overall r-value on the correlation between the level of social skills and the level of psychological well-being of students was 0.670 with $p < 0.05$, which means that the social skills are significantly associated with psychological well-being of students. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 5.2. Significance on the Relationship between Social Skills and Psychological Well-Being of Students

Social Skills of Students	Psychological Well-Being of Students						Overall
	autonomy	environmental mastery	personal growth	positive relations	purpose in life	self-acceptance	
Communication	.403* (0.000)	.373* (0.000)	.476* (0.000)	.232* (0.000)	.446* (0.000)	.383* (0.000)	.523* (0.000)
Cooperation	.395* (0.000)	.348* (0.000)	.444* (0.000)	.179* (0.000)	.366* (0.000)	.239* (0.000)	.444* (0.000)
Assertion	.382* (0.000)	.283* (0.000)	.331* (0.000)	.213* (0.000)	.252* (0.000)	.336* (0.000)	.407* (0.000)
Responsibility	.333* (0.000)	.295* (0.000)	.441* (0.000)	.217* (0.000)	.438* (0.000)	.238* (0.000)	.443* (0.000)
Empathy	.312* (0.000)	.218* (0.000)	.369* (0.000)	.185* (0.001)	.285* (0.000)	.218* (0.000)	.358* (0.000)
Engagement	.405* (0.000)	.385* (0.000)	.371* (0.000)	.353* (0.000)	.382* (0.000)	.378* (0.000)	.516* (0.000)
self-control	.471* (0.000)	.359* (0.000)	.476* (0.000)	.244* (0.000)	.351* (0.000)	.267* (0.000)	.490* (0.000)
Overall	.571* (0.000)	.475* (0.000)	.611* (0.000)	.345* (0.000)	.528* (0.000)	.434* (0.000)	.670* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level

Moreover, when the domains of social skills of students such as the communication, cooperation, assertion, responsibility, empathy, engagement and self-control, were correlated to the overall psychological well-being of students, results yielded the r-values of 0.523, 0.444, 0.407, 0.0443, 0.358, .516 and 0.490 with the p-values of less than 0.05, respectively, which can be all interpreted as significant. These factors are significantly related to the domains of psychological well-being of students, such as autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations, purpose in life, and learning and self-acceptance. This indicates the importance of interpersonal abilities in contributing to mental and emotional health among students. This association further suggests that fostering and enhancing social skills may positively impact the overall psychological well-being of students. This corroborates with the proposition of several authors (Hendren et al, 2014; Nair, Ravindranath & Thomas, 2013) that social skills can predict psychological wellbeing. Developing the social skills of students helps them to be capable of overcoming problems that negatively affect their psychological well-being.

Significance on the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Psychological Well-Being of Students

This present study also aimed to determine whether emotional intelligence has a significant relationship with the psychological well-being of students. The results of the computations are shown in Table 5.3.

Table 5.3. Significance on the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Psychological Well-Being of Students

Emotional Intelligence of Students	Psychological Well-Being of Students						Overall
	Autonomy	Environmental Mastery	Personal Growth	Positive relation	Purpose in Life	Self-Acceptance	
Self-Awareness	.471* (0.000)	.497* (0.000)	.534* (0.000)	.306* (0.000)	.510* (0.000)	.374* (0.000)	.608* (0.000)
Self-Regulation	.478* (0.000)	.475* (0.000)	.545* (0.000)	.320* (0.000)	.514* (0.000)	.380* (0.000)	.613* (0.000)
Motivation	.532* (0.000)	.542* (0.000)	.589* (0.000)	.418* (0.000)	.542* (0.000)	.408* (0.000)	.686* (0.000)
Social-Awareness/Empathy	.469* (0.000)	.448* (0.000)	.512* (0.000)	.339* (0.000)	.527* (0.000)	.372* (0.000)	.603* (0.000)
Social Skills	.565* (0.000)	.569* (0.000)	.608* (0.000)	.354* (0.001)	.490* (0.000)	.495* (0.000)	.697* (0.000)
Overall	.611* (0.000)	.614* (0.000)	.676* (0.000)	.345* (0.000)	.626* (0.000)	.493* (0.000)	.778* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level

As shown in the table, the overall r-value on the correlation between the level of emotional intelligence and the level of psychological well-being of students was 0.778 with $p < 0.05$, which means that the emotional intelligence is significantly associated with students' psychological well-being. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected.

In addition, when the domains of emotional intelligence of students such as the self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, social awareness/empathy, and social skills, were correlated to the overall psychological well-being of students, results of yielded the r-values of 0.608, 0.613, 0.686, 0.603, and 0.697 with the p-values of less than 0.05, respectively, which can be all interpreted as significant. These factors are significantly related to the domains of psychological well-being of students, such as the autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations, purpose in life, and learning, and self-acceptance.

This suggests that students with higher emotional intelligence may experience enhanced mental and emotional health. This association underscores the potential importance of developing and nurturing emotional intelligence skills for the overall well-being of students. This confirms the propositions of numerous authors (Alvarez et al., 2016; Fernandez-Berrocal, 2016; Martins et al., 2010; Schutte et al., 2007) stating that improving emotional intelligence would promote well-being.

Goodness of Fit Measures of the Three Path Analysis Models

To come up with the best-fit path model for the psychological well-being of students, path model was applied to three hypothesized models.

Generated Model 1. Shown in Figure 2 is Hypothesized Model 1 in standardized solution. It is a tested model depicting the interrelationships between the latent exogenous variables and its direct causal relation to the endogenous variable psychological well-being. The findings indicate that both social skills of students and emotional intelligence of students directly contribute to psychological well-being of students. Furthermore, there is a significant correlation between social skills of students and emotional intelligence of students. Additionally, social skills of students and emotional intelligence of students have an impact on parents as social context, with these two exogenous variables directly influencing psychological well-being of students.

Figure 2. Path Analysis Model 1 in Standardized Solution Showing the Direct Influence of Social Skills of Students and Emotional Intelligence of Students on Psychological Well-Being

Legend: SocialSkillsOfStudents, Social Skills of Students; ParentsAsSocialContext, Parents as Social Context; EmotionalIntelligenceOfStudents, Emotional Intelligence of Students; PsychologicalWellBeingOfStudents, Psychological Well-Being of Students

Presenting the fitness of the measurements, the results in Table 8 showed the descriptive statistics correlations matrix of the measured variables. The first step was to screen to find outliers and to examine missing data, as well as to assess the linearity and normality of the data that the model did not match the data. The first generated structural model displayed in Figure 2, showed the interrelationships of the exogenous variables: parents as social context, social skills and emotional intelligence, and its causal relationships on the psychological well-being and the RMSEA was 0.202 and CMIN/DF was 15.276 and these indices did not reach the acceptable ranges.

Table 6. Goodness of Fit Measures of Path Analysis Model 1

INDEX	CRITERION	MODEL FIT VALUE
P-Close	> 0.05	.001
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	15.276
P-value	> 0.05	.000
GFI	> 0.95	.979
CFI	> 0.95	.980
NFI	> 0.95	.979
TLI	> 0.95	.882
RMSEA	< 0.05	.202

CMIN/DF, Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom; NFI, Normed Fit Index; TLI, Tucker-Lewis Index; CFI, Comparative Fit Index; GFI, Goodness of Fit Index; RMSEA, Root Means Square of Error Approximation; P-close, P of Close Fit; P-value, Probability Level

Generated Model 2. Displayed in the generated Model 2 in Figure 3 are the interrelationships of the exogenous variable and its causal relationship to the psychological well-being of students as endogenous variable. A model variation approach (Kline, 2005) was acceptable by testing the hypothesized model and removing indicators or variables to improve the fit of the data. Shown in Table 8 is the fit model 2. The CFI was 0.995, NFI was 0.994, and TLI was 0.973, which meant fit for the model. However, the indications of CMIN/DF = 4.267 has its conforming p-value = 0.039, while the RMSEA = 0.097 with P-close = 0.130. With these, the model discovered to be a poor fit because not all its indices reached the acceptable ranges. Hence; since all the indices did not meet the

criterion, it is a poor fit.

Figure 3. Path Analysis Model 2 in Standardized Solution Showing the Direct Influence of Emotional Intelligence of Students on Psychological Well-Being

Legend: SocialSkillsOfStudents, Social Skills of Students; ParentsAsSocialContext, Parents as Social Context; EmotionalIntelligenceOfStudents, Emotional Intelligence of Students; PsychologicalWellBeingOfStudents, Psychological Well-Being of Students

Table 7. Goodness of Fit Measures of Path Analysis Model 2

INDEX	CRITERION	MODEL FIT VALUE
P-Close	> 0.05	.130
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	4.267
P-value	> 0.05	.039
GFI	> 0.95	.994
CFI	> 0.95	.995
NFI	> 0.95	.994
TLI	> 0.95	.973
RMSEA	< 0.05	.097

CMIN/DF, Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom; NFI, Normed Fit Index; TLI, Tucker-Lewis Index; CFI, Comparative Fit Index; GFI, Goodness of Fit Index; RMSEA, Root Means Square of Error Approximation; P-close, P of Close Fit; P-value, Probability Level

Generated Model 3. Model 3 came out as the best-fit path model satisfying the criteria for the standard-fit because of the causal model data fitting using Pearson r, which should be significant. Other criteria to be considered to have a good model fit are as follows: a value of 0.95 or greater for CFI, which is the comparative fit index (Byrne, 2001), RMSEA value of less than 0.05, which is the root means square of error approximation (Meyers, Gamst, & Guarino, 2006), NFI or normed fit index value of more than 0.95 (Hu and Bentler, 1999). Model 3 has satisfied all these criteria, showing that the NFI is 0.998 more than 0.95, the CFI is 0.999 greater than 0.95, and TLI is 0.994 greater than 0.95. Also, the indications of CMIN/DF = 1.723 with its conforming p-value = 0.189, while the RMSEA is 0.046 less than 0.05 with P-close = 0.365 which is greater than 0.05. The graph of the path model is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Path Analysis Model 3 in Standardized Solution Showing the Direct Influence of Social Skills of Students and Emotional Intelligence of Students on Psychological Well-Being

Legend: SocialSkillsOfStudents, Social Skills of Students; ParentsAsSocialContext, Parents as Social Context; EmotionalIntelligenceOfStudents, Emotional Intelligence of Students; PsychologicalWellBeingOfStudents, Psychological Well-Being of Students

Table 8. *Goodness of Fit Measures of Path Analysis Model 3*

<i>INDEX</i>	<i>CRITERION</i>	<i>MODEL FIT VALUE</i>
P-Close	> 0.05	.365
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	1.723
P-value	> 0.05	.189
GFI	> 0.95	.998
CFI	> 0.95	.999
NFI	> 0.95	.998
TLI	> 0.95	.994
RMSEA	< 0.05	.046

CMIN/DF, Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom; NFI, Normed Fit Index; TLI, Tucker-Lewis Index; CFI, Comparative Fit Index; GFI, Goodness of Fit Index; RMSEA, Root Means Square of Error Approximation; P-close, P of Close Fit; P-value, Probability Level

Regarding the sample size, this study exceeds the minimum acceptable size of 200 for path analysis, as recommended by Boomsma (1982). The overall sample of 400 indicates that the study's sample size is sufficient for obtaining a well-fitting model. Model 3, derived from a more intricate theoretical framework, eliminates weak influencing variables that were not significantly linked to other variables in previous models. Additionally, the model presented in Figure 4, illustrating the direct and indirect influence of exogenous variables on the endogenous variable, integrates various theories and concepts drawn from relevant literature.

The Model 3 in Standardized Solution provides analysis on the interrelationships among the variables of the study and assessment of model fit. As shown in the Appended Figure 4, the amount of variance explained by the combined influence of parents as social context, social skills, and emotional intelligence on the psychological well-being of students is 63%. Hence, it can be gleaned that 63% of the variance of the psychological well-being of students can be attributed to the combined influence of students' parents as social context, social skills, and emotional intelligence.

Data specifically reveals that the parents as social context (beta=0.14), social skills (beta= 0.11), and emotional intelligence (beta= 0.65) have direct influence on the organizational commitment of teachers. This finding of the study further substantiates the proposition of various researchers who have presented that the parents as social context of a child contributes to overall psychological well-being (Gupta & Mehtani, 2015), social skills can predict psychological wellbeing Hendren et al, 2014; Nair, Ravindranath & Thomas, 2013), and emotional intelligence influences well-being (Alvarez et al., 2016; Fernandez-Berrocal, 2016; Martins et al., 2010; Schutte et al., 2007).

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, conclusions were drawn as follows:

The descriptive level of the exogenous variables: parents as social context, social skills, and emotional intelligence of students were high. Meanwhile, the endogenous variable – psychological well-being of students, with a high descriptive level. All variables are oftentimes manifested. There was a significant relationship between parents as social context and psychological well-being of students, and social skills were also significantly correlated with the psychological well-being of students. Also, there was a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological well-being of students.

The path model indicates the best fit model for the psychological well-being of students as proven by the summary of the goodness of fit satisfying all the indices for a path model. The significant direct effect of parents as social context, social skills, and emotional intelligence of students on their psychological well-being implies the importance of the above exogenous factors in understanding and promoting the psychological well-being of students. The study is based on Ryan and Deci's Self-Determination Theory (2007), which emphasizes eudaimonic well-being characterized by vitality, self-awareness, and self-regulated behavior, rather than external rewards or status. It focuses on the integrated functioning of the self and factors like emotional intelligence and social influences, such as parental upbringing, that contribute to psychological well-being.

Finally, findings indicated that parents as social context, social skills and emotional intelligence were significantly correlated with the psychological well-being of students. Model 3 came out as the best-fit path model that predicted the psychological well-being of students as it was significantly influenced by social skills of students, parents as social context and emotional intelligence. Social skills of students revealed a significant predictor of parents as social context while the emotional intelligence showed a significant correlation with students' social skills. Hence, schools may consider enhancing the psychological well-being of students by developing their social skills and enhancing their emotional intelligence. Also, encourage parents' engagement in school activities.

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are suggested.

It was revealed that the following indicators got the lowest means: chaos for parents as social context indicating that this aspect is somewhat prevented; self-control for social skills; social skills for emotional intelligence, and self-acceptance for psychological well-being. Hence, the Department of Education considering chaos in parents as a social context suggested a need for interventions to create a more stable and supportive home environment. For instance, parenting workshops can be designed to equip parents with effective strategies, communication skills, and the ability to create a stable home environment, particularly focusing on reducing chaos within

the family context. Further, to enhance students' self-control in social interactions, the school heads together with the teachers may incorporate social skills training programs within the educational curriculum could be beneficial. Embedding a comprehensive social skills training curriculum into the academic framework can enhance students' self-control in social interactions. This curriculum might include modules on emotional regulation, active listening, and conflict resolution.

Additionally, classroom teachers may recognize the link between social skills and emotional intelligence, integrating emotional intelligence education into the curriculum may foster improved interpersonal relationships. Integrating emotional intelligence education into the curriculum would further bolster students' social skills within the context of emotional intelligence, fostering improved interpersonal relationships. Also, addressing self-acceptance as a component of psychological well-being through dedicated well-being initiatives could contribute to building positive self-esteem. Collaborating with mental health professionals may further strengthen these initiatives, providing specialized support and resources. These practical recommendations aim to enhance specific aspects, fostering a more holistic and conducive learning environment for students within the educational system.

Further, given the findings that the best-fitting model indicates significant direct effects of parents as a social context, social skills, and emotional intelligence on the psychological well-being of students, it is recommended that schools may implement targeted interventions. These interventions could include workshops for parents to enhance their supportive role, integration of social skills training into the curriculum, and initiatives that promote emotional intelligence education. Additionally, school policies and programs should prioritize creating a positive and nurturing environment that recognizes the interconnectedness of these factors and their impact on students' overall well-being.

For future researchers exploring the relationships between parents as a social context, social skills, emotional intelligence, and the psychological well-being of students, several recommendations can guide their investigations. Complementing quantitative findings with qualitative research, such as interviews, can offer a more in-depth exploration of the subjective experiences of students. Moreover, designing and implementing intervention studies will be crucial in assessing the effectiveness of targeted programs and evaluating outcomes over time. Exploring and comparing relationships across different educational levels will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the variables of the study. Also, ensuring diversity in study samples, encompassing students from various backgrounds, will enhance the generalizability of findings. These recommendations collectively aim to enrich future research endeavors in uncovering the nature of the interactions between these factors and students' psychological well-being.

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